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**EXISTENTIAL NIGERIANISM AND RESPONSIBLE CITIZENSHIP:
EVALUATING INDIVIDUAL DUTIES TOWARDS NATION BUILDING**

ABSTRACT

There are no two persons who were born the same way, at the same time, by the same person, and in the same place. Not even two identical twins, for one must come out first before the other. This is clear proof that in each one of us, there is an individuality that cannot be negated. It is this individuality that makes each person unique. Yet, each person is born into a community of persons, making them social beings. A human being, therefore, is both an individual being and a social being. The ability to navigate this trajectory of individualism in a society of persons and assume responsibilities that are necessary from both wings makes an authentic person. In the authenticity of individuals, societies are formidably built to stand strong, and in the making of sacrifices, standing societies stand out in development. Abnegation of responsibilities brings about delays in community development. This is indeed bad faith. Whereas commitment brings development, bad faith brings stagnation and retardation. Nigeria has suffered a lot of stagnation and retardation in many aspects of its national life. This research aims to use the postulations of existentialism to arouse individual responsibilities towards nation-building. It recommends strong individual commitments as a possible way towards nation-building. It adopts an analytical method of study and concludes that, following the provisions of existentialism as a movement, the glorious days of Nigeria will soon be manifest, and the journey to a great and formidable nation will again be feasible.

Keywords: Existentialism, individuality, responsibility, commitment, development.

INTRODUCTION

Some years ago, the then-President of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Dr. Goodluck Ebele Jonathan, claimed that he was the most criticized president in the world¹. Yes, the truth is that a large chunk of Nigerians criticized him, even though I may not be exact with the ratio of his critics. However, those who negatively criticized him were more than those who applauded him. Of course, in my assessment, I don't even think he did so well, except that his best is too weak to move Nigeria forward on the fast lane. But I get offended when people who are misbehaving also criticize him, even at the moment of their misdeeds. Nigeria is the way it is because we have many very passive citizens who do not bother about their input in moving Nigeria to a better level of existence. We have people who exist in a way, but not in the real sense of existence, in the sense of what existentialists call existence. For one to exist in the sense of existentialism, he has to be an active actor, not a passive one. For Soren Kierkegaard, those who are passive in existence and do not determine the course of their existence are mere spectators, as different from actors. Actors are those who determine the course of their existence. The resultant effect of the passivity of many Nigerians is the deep slide of the country into the present state of political instability, bad governance, economic hardships, social unrest, and horrible insecurity. In life, if you do not actively choose your path, events will drag you to paths you had never prepared for. Can we say that Nigerians determine their existence? We rarely determine our fate. We were born into our families without any contribution; we did not choose our parents, nor did we choose our siblings or other relatives. Most of us were sent to schools of our parents' choice based on their financial strength, without consideration of the children's own choices. The results of our elections hardly reflect the true state of the votes of the people. Sometimes, national external factors are used to determine the fate of the citizens. A country where the citizens depend on the government instead of the reverse cannot claim to have any atom of the convictions of existentialism working in it. Although existentialism is an individualistic philosophy, Nigeria cannot claim any bit of existence in the sense of existentialism, both as individual citizens and as a nation. Yet, Nigeria needs to exist in that sense before it can move forward. We have not told ourselves that we are not just Nigerians, but we are Nigeria. Each of us must exist as both a Nigerian and Nigeria in the sense of existentialism, to move our country, Nigeria, forward. We must realize first, as individuals, that we are responsible for whatever life we live; if Nigeria is great, we are the actors,

¹ Goodluck Jonathan, "Jonathan: I'm the Most Criticized President in the World", *PMNews* (<https://pmnewsnigeria.com>, 08/27/2012), 1.

and if Nigeria is ridiculed in the face of the world, we are also responsible for it. Each person in Nigeria must wake up and take the challenges facing Nigeria as their problem.

EXISTENTIALISM AS A CONCEPT

There has never been a general agreement on the definition of the term existentialism. The first prominent existentialist philosopher to adopt the term as a self-description is Jean-Paul Sartre. However, existentialism as a term has been applied to many philosophers in hindsight. As Steven Crowell said, "...defining existentialism has been relatively difficult, and he argues that it is better understood as a general approach used to reject certain systematic philosophies rather than as a systematic philosophy."² We shall therefore strive more to understand the concept of existentialism instead of defining it. Existentialism could be better described as a movement rather than a school of thought. Joseph Omoregbe gave it one of the most suitable descriptions. According to him, "Existentialism is not a homogenous school the members of which hold basically the same doctrine as is the case, for example, with Thomism."³ The term itself derives from the 'existence', and it dates back to Kierkegaard, the father of existentialism. But its meaning differs from the ordinary meaning of existence. In ordinary usage, we can talk of the existence of a stone, the existence of a tree, or of an animal. But in existentialism, existence is restricted to human existence with all its characteristic features. Only human beings exist; all other kinds of beings are, but do not exist. Martin Heidegger expresses this by saying: "The being that exists is man. Man alone exists. Trees are, but they do not exist. Angels are, but they do not exist. God is, but he does not exist."⁴ Existentialism, therefore, is a philosophy of human existence.⁵ Existentialism is a philosophy that emphasizes the uniqueness and isolation of the individual experience in a hostile or indifferent universe. It came as a reaction against the abstraction of Hegelian idealism.⁶ This philosophy regards human existence as unexplainable and stresses freedom of choice and responsibility for the consequences of one's acts. Its intention is to show people their own obligation to secure their existence

² Wikipedia, *Existentialism* in <http://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/existentialism>, retrieved on 25-09-2012 via <http://www.googlesearch.com>.

³ Joseph Omoregbe, *A Simplified History of Western Philosophy, Volume 3: Contemporary Philosophy* (Lagos: Joja Educational Research and Publishers Ltd, 1199), 38.

⁴ Martin Heidegger, "The Way Book into the Ground of Metaphysics," in *Existentialism from Dostoyevsky to Sartre*, ed. W. Kaufman (New York: Meridian Books, Inc., 1956), 215.

⁵ Joseph Omoregbe, *A Simplified History of Western Philosophy*, Vol 3, 38.

⁶ *Ibid*, 39.

(identity) by realizing how they define themselves as separate from anything that blurs individual identities.

An easy way to understand existentialism as a concept is to think about how we are generalized into groups or types of people, and how that negates our significance. To do something because you are part of a group or want to be accepted into one (following trends, for example) nullifies your identity. You exist only as part of a group. But to make a choice separate yourself from the influence of anything except yourself (for example, because you genuinely want to) secures you as a unique and significant human being. Existentialists argue that not thinking and acting towards determining your place in the universe essentially makes your existence meaningless. Existentialism, as a general belief, is a 20th-century cultural movement, primarily literary, theological, and philosophical, that recognizes the free individual as the sole creator of meaning and morality.⁷ Omoregbe argues that it is a 19th century movement whose major proponents include; Karl Jaspers(1883-1969), Martin Heidegger(1889-1976), Gabriel Marcel(1889-1973), Jean-Paul Sartre(1905-1980), Maurice Merleau-Ponty(1908-1961) and Albert Camus(1913-1960). There are also Italian, Spanish, Russian, and Jewish representatives such as Abbagnano, Unamuno, Berdyaev, and Buber.

SOME THEMES IN EXISTENTIALISM

The most popular theme in existentialism is found in the Sartrean dictum, “Existence precedes Essence”; that is, the existence of the individual, both factually and logically, comes before the meaning that he or she gives to the world. Other themes include irrationalism, man and the world, the others, freedom, choice and responsibility, commitment, anguish, and bad faith.

Existence Precedes Essence: Existence precedes essence is best understood in contrast to an established principle of metaphysics that essence precedes existence as found in the traditional philosophies of Plato, Aristotle, Hegel, Spinoza, and other traditional philosophers before existentialism. They claim that there is such a thing as human nature, determined by the cosmic order (or a god), laid down by religious tradition, or legislated by political or social authority. For example, that man is a rational being. To Sartre, the idea that “existence precedes essence” means that a personality is not built over a previously designed model or a precise purpose, because it is the human being

⁷ Scientology Beliefs, *What is Existentialism*, retrieved through <http://wiki.answers.com>, 26-09-12.

who chooses to engage in such an enterprise. This was a reaction against Spinoza's speculation that man is determined by what surrounds him.⁸ Man determines and creates his own life. For Sartre, therefore, an oppressive situation is not intolerable in itself, but once regarded as such by those who feel oppressed, the situation becomes intolerable.

Irrationality: Existentialism arose largely as a reaction to rationalism. Soren Kierkegaard started the movement in reaction against Hegel's abstraction and exaggerated confidence in the power of human reason.⁹ He frowned at Hegel's bold claim to have been able to encompass the whole of reality within his speculative system. Just like Rationalism emanated as a reaction against the faith of the Middle Ages, in the same way, existentialism came as a reaction against Rationalism. Darwin's *Origin of Species* (1859) struck a heavy blow on rationalism by its claim that reason is the product of matter and man the product of the blind evolutionary process.¹⁰ Arthur Schopenhauer (1788-1860) identified the ultimate reality, the Absolute, not as reason but as Will to live.¹¹ There is a limit to which it can go, but it cannot account for all things. For this reason, Nietzsche embarked on his program of the transvaluation of values.

Man, and His World: The existentialists see man and his world as inseparably linked together. Man, in the words of Heidegger, is a being-in-the-world. It is only in the world that man can realize himself and become conscious of his being. In the world, man does not just have a body, but he is the body.

Man, and Others: Man is not only a being-in-the-world but a being-with-others. He lives in the world and does the work. The fact that there are others says Sartre is incontestable and touches the heart, yet each person is unique; he has his own time to live and his death to die.

Freedom, Choice, and Responsibility: Freedom for existentialists is not a property of the will but the very structure of the being of man. Man, says Sartre, is condemned to be free. Freedom is identical with him, that even if a person refuses to make a choice, that very act of not making a choice is a choice in itself. Therefore, Sartre says, "It is necessary to point out to common sense... that the

⁸ Mulla Sdra, *Existence Precedes Essence* retrieved from <http://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Existence> precedes essence, through <http://www.googlesearch.com> on 28-09-12.

⁹ Soren Kierkegaard, *Concluding Unscientific Postscript* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1941), 99-133.

¹⁰ Joseph Omoregbe, *A Simplified History of Western Philosophy*, Vol 3, 41.

¹¹ *Ibid.*

formula 'to be free' does not mean 'to obtain what one has wished', but rather by oneself to determine oneself to wish (in the sense of choosing)..."¹² Therefore, on trying to explain the world of Being and Nothingness, Istvan Meszaros said that, "...all the principal categories hinge on 'being'.... Existentialism defines man through action, and that existentialism is 'a morality of action and of commitment, we witness a significant shift of emphasis which opens up new possibilities of tangible social and political involvement in his post-war development."¹³

Freedom, therefore, which forms the core of human existence, becomes the core of human development and self-actualization. "Man's freedom elevates him above the past, the environment, the rules of language, and the dialectics of history."¹⁴ Therefore, the human person becomes a self-determining agent; not just a being unto others, but also a being unto himself. It therefore means that human freedom brings about some degree of responsibility. Omoregbe says, "Man's freedom is inseparably accompanied by a heavy responsibility, for man is responsible for the way he uses his freedom."¹⁵ If man is responsible for the way he uses his freedom, it simply means that the human person is liable for whatever is the product of his actions, good or evil, success or failure. It therefore also follows that man should be the deciding agent of his own actions, both as individuals and as a society.

Anguish and Bad Faith: When man sees the radical nature of his freedom with its concomitant responsibility, he comes to realize that freedom is a heavy burden. He is then seized with anguish, and he tries in vain to run away from it through various devices. The act of running away from his freedom and its responsibility is bad faith or self-deception, for in reality, man can never run away from his freedom, since freedom is identical with his existence. Man is therefore 'condemned to be free'. He is thrown into freedom, and there is no running away from it.

Commitment: The existentialists propose that since man is identical with his freedom and cannot run away from it, he should not be afraid to commit himself. Freedom must be committed to action. Anybody seeking freedom without commitment is only deceiving themselves. In his trilogy, *Les Chemins*

¹² Jean-Paul Sartre, *Being and Nothingness* (New York: Methuen and Co. Ltd, 1956), 444.

¹³ Istvan Meszaros, *The Work of Sartre, Vol. 1: Search for Freedom* (Great Britain: The Harvester Press Ltd, 1979), 156.

¹⁴ Omoregbe, *A Simplified History of Western Philosophy*, Vol. 3, 46.

¹⁵ *Ibid*, 47.

de la Liberté, Sartre portrays Mathieu as a man who deceives himself by refusing to commit himself in any way. All he wants, he says, is to be free. For this reason, he refuses to marry, and when he discovers that his girlfriend is pregnant with him, he decides on abortion, rather than marriage. But he realizes later that he is deceiving himself. 'I am free,' he said to himself... he stopped and began to laugh.¹⁶ Freedom is so near, yet we seek it far away. Each person has their freedom. For human reality, Sartre believes, to be is to act, and to cease to act is to cease to be.¹⁷ It all points to the fact that living in the pretence that you are being determined is unhealthy and cannot help anybody develop. In the words of Martin Heidegger, running away from our responsibility is an inauthentic life.¹⁸ Could our country, Nigeria, be suffering from what Sartre calls bad faith or what Heidegger calls inauthentic life? A review of the Philosophy of existentialism in the light of Sartre's philosophy will aid us in understanding.

A REVIEW OF SARTRE'S PHILOSOPHY OF EXISTENTIALISM IN THE LIGHT OF NIGERIAN EXISTENCE

From the themes in Existentialism, we have reviewed the views of a few existentialists, including Kierkegaard, Heidegger, Sartre, and others. In this section, we are concerned with how these views can help us develop our country, Nigeria. There is no doubt that the level of existence taking place in Nigeria is the type that leaves the people desiring to be in every other place but Nigeria. This could be responsible for the mass exodus of Nigerians into different parts of the world. Nigeria can be as great as Europe and the developed parts of the world. We shall see how these views of the existentialists, especially Sartre's view, can help Nigeria to get to such heights.

Nigeria is a place where people scarcely accept the responsibility for their actions, especially if it is negative. According to Leo Buscaglia, "I think we have been brought up to do things under duress and fear that we have somehow lost the notion of doing the right thing simply because it is right."¹⁹ That means we are brought up in the mood that we fear responsibilities, yet, "if we wish to be free from enslavement, we must choose freedom and the responsibility this entails."²⁰ As Sartre told us, freedom is the self-deciding power of the individual

¹⁶ Sartre, *Les Chemins la Liberte*, vol. 2, Le sursts.

¹⁷ Sartre, *L'Existentialisme est un Humanisme* (Paris: Nagel, 1970), 486-487.

¹⁸ Omoregbe, *A Simplified History of Western Philosophy*, Vol. 3, 71-75

¹⁹ Leo Buscaglia, *its on You (Our Responsibility to Nigeria) – Politics –Nairaland* (<http://www.nairaland.com/951634/Responsibility-nigeria>) on 07-10-12.

²⁰ Ibid.

and must go with responsibility. For instance, on the 1st of October, we celebrated sixty-four years of Nigerian independence. In the past, I posed a question, asking if Nigeria is truly free. The answers I got showed that Nigeria only claims to be free, but it is not free for many people. But I would rather borrow the words of Jean-Jacques Rousseau that Nigeria is free, but everywhere in chains. To what extent do Nigerians decide their fate without the interference of the United States of America? But if Nigeria does not get support from America and other organizations to what extent can it take care of its needs? To what extent has Nigeria combated the menace of bombing by Boko Haram and kidnapping by Niger Delta militants. When Nigeria was listed as one of the terrorist countries, many Nigerians criticized America for enlisting Nigeria as such. Can we still say that we are a non-terrorist state? Sometime in 2011, Nigeria was warned against flooding. In the name of freedom without responsibility, the federal government did nothing to fight that natural disaster that finally caught us. Even with the warning of great winds to come during the dry season of the same year,²¹ in response to climate change, many Nigerians did not take simple steps such as planting trees to curb such harsh weather. Both as a country and as citizens, we like freedom but avoid responsibilities.

Born in 1905 in Paris and having taught philosophy in a lycée in Le Havre and also having experienced the lawlessness of war during the Second World War, during which he wrote his *Being and Nothingness*, Sartre understood the fact that whatever life a man lives is all dependent on him. Invariably, for Nigeria to achieve any standard, Nigerians, both as leaders and citizens, must be ready to define the kind of life that they want both for themselves and the country. Most times, we run to the African Union (A.U.), the United States, China, and other countries, but these people cannot design Nigeria better than Nigerians. Only Nigerians can understand how to design their country both as individuals and as a country. If somebody else will help, such help must hang on what Nigerians tell them. But on the contrary, Nigeria has suffered colonialism and is still suffering neo-colonialism. Our policies are made overseas and brought to the national and state Houses just to fulfil all formalities, our currencies are printed outside Nigeria, our elections are decided outside our country; one can understand why the president of our great country is constantly on the road, travelling from one country to another. Our country is ruled from outside of itself, and we cannot determine our lives by ourselves. Existential Nigerianism

²¹ Nigeria Daily News, *Nigeria: New Weather Warning After Devastating Floods* (<http://www.nigeriadailynews.com/africa/46046-nigeria-news-warning-after-devastating-floods.html>) on 07-10-12.

postulates a more active involvement of Nigerians in determining their fate towards nation-building. It calls for responsible citizenship and commitments of individuals in their various duties. It avers that when all Nigerians commit to their individual duties in sincerity, with existential consciousness towards nation building, the resultant effect will be a great Nigeria.

Secondly, man is a being-unto-the-world and unto others. Can we claim that Nigerians are sufficiently beings-unto-one-another? A country where people do not mostly act for national development but for selfish wealth, where most leaders do not even care about leadership but money-sharing formula, a country where many teachers are cheaters, a lot of doctors are killers, are its citizens beings-unto-the-country. Nigeria cannot claim innocence of a number of these allegations. There is a high-level insensitivity and indifference in many national and state sectors when it comes to duty for duty's sake without attachment of strings. Nigeria must adopt Immanuel Kant's idea of duty for duty sake, to do what ought to be done. When it is done because others need it, then there is existence unto others. We must learn to be beings-unto-ourselves and unto our country first, then we can be beings unto other nations.

Nigerians must accept their freedom and their commitment to their responsibilities. Sometime in 2011, the then president of the Federal Republic of Nigeria denied the bombing in Abuja on October 1st having any link with MEND, only for the said group to come and claim responsibility for the incident. Responsibilities must become serious issues. People should answer for their actions irrespective of their connections and relationships. We must not forget that Sartre said that trying to run away from responsibility brings about bad faith. If faith is a name given to life in Nigeria, can we call life in Nigeria good faith? In other words, can we call life in Nigeria a good life? If life in Nigeria is not good, we can also call it bad faith if faith could be used interchangeably with life. Bad faith in existentialism is running away from responsibilities. We must take up our social, political, religious, and academic responsibilities. We must take up the responsibility of assessing the state of our nation and sincerely step up our commitment towards building a strong and formidable society.

EVALUATION

As its name suggests, existentialism is a movement on human existence. However, existence for existentialists does not mean the same thing in its common sense. For existentialists, existence means action. They believe that by actively being involved in determining your own life, you exist. This was posited first by Soren Kierkegaard and then by Simone de Beauvoir. In her book, *The*

Second Sex, de Beauvoir posited that “one is not born a woman but becomes one.”²² She showed that each person decides his or her being. Both Simone de Beauvoir and Kierkegaard influenced Jean-Paul Sartre. Sartre was also influenced by his belief in atheism. For him, there is no God. If there is no God, then human beings have no boundaries in deciding their fate. Therefore, freedom becomes a necessary part of the human person who exists unto himself, unto others, and unto the whole universe. Therefore, the product of his actions should be linked to him; thus, he should be responsible for his actions.

Being influenced by these factors, Sartre posited that existence precedes essence. In other words, people first exist, confront themselves, emerge in the world, and define themselves afterwards.²³ Therefore, each person is what he makes of himself. Sartre was reacting to Spinoza, who postulated that man is determined by what surrounds him. An average Nigerian would simply subscribe to the belief that Nigeria’s underdevelopment, corruption, and bad leadership are caused by others, not Nigerians. It is easily heard that whatever happens to a Nigerian, even sickness and pains, is attributed to some human agents. Even if one who suffers from malaria and typhoid fever does not believe they were caused by mosquito bites and bad water, respectively, they must be linked to some human agents. Such is life for those who avoid the responsibility of their actions.

Sartre’s philosophy of existence brings existence and responsibility into one page. The adoption of its position will lead to national development in Nigeria. However, we criticize Sartre’s existentialism as not accounting for political and institutional creations’ inequality among persons and obstacles for some but not for all.²⁴ Sartre talks about human freedom as an integral part of human beings but does not tell us how to manage our freedom in the society.

CONCLUSION

Life is what one makes out of it. Many Nigerians are yet to understand this truth in real sense of existence. As such, a number of people fail to do the right thing at the right time. Consequently, unpleasant outcomes are often the impeding realities. This study set out to reawaken in Nigerians and by extension, other people who find themselves in this position of laxity towards their destiny,

²² Samuel Enoch Stumpf, *Philosophy: History and Problems*, 5th edition (U.S.A: McGraw-Hill, 1994), 509.

²³ *Ibid*, 512.

²⁴ Kulturkritik, A Critique of Sartre’s Existentialism (<http://socyberty.com/philosopher>), retrieved on 07-10-12.

the need to take their existence into their hands. An escape route of pushing everything to God or other divinities will not solve our problems. Without doubting the existence of God, like Sartre, Nigerian citizens need to brace up to decide their fate, within the limits that God has enabled them. Nigerians must take their fate into their hands in determining their leaders, their actions, and their circumstances. Nigerians clamour for freedom and must realize that "...man being condemned to be free carries the weight of the whole world on his shoulders; he is responsible for the world and for himself as a way of being."²⁵ Nigerians vote (whether by election or selection) their leaders in and should also accept the responsibility for their actions. Since we made them our leaders, we are also part of their decisions. To excuse ourselves from the guilt of their actions, we must not contribute to leading them. Accepting the responsibility of our actions makes us authentic (in the words of Martin Heidegger), but running away from our responsibility amounts to what Sartre calls bad faith. A great number of the Nigerian predicaments arise from this bad faith, a situation of avoiding our responsibility. No body, from the leaders to the followers wants to own up their responsibility. The truth is that "...we have the power to create ourselves."²⁶ We are the architects of the way we are and we are the ones to change our story.

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²⁵ The Philosopher's Lighthouse, *Sartre's Thoughts on Freedom* in *Oracle ThinkQuest* (<http://library.thinkquest.org> retrieved on 07-10-12).

²⁶ *Sartre's Summary* (<http://www.sonoma.edu/users/d/daniels/sartre%20sum.html>), retrieved on 07-10-12.

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